

Investigation of Neutron Noise Phenomena in Multiplying Breeding Blankets of Fusion Reactors

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ABSTRACT

This study presents an investigation into the feasibility of applying neutron noise analysis techniques to the multiplying breeding blankets of Tokamak-type fusion reactors. Neutron noise methods, commonly used in research fission reactor diagnostics, have not yet been explored in the fusion context, particularly in systems involving strong (n,2n) multiplication reactions. Using the Monte Carlo particle transport code OpenMC, a simplified model of a Tokamak breeding blanket containing beryllium as a neutron multiplier was simulated. A virtual neutron detector was positioned outside the blanket region to catch the temporal neutron flux fluctuations arising from Be (n,2n) reactions. The resulting time series were analyzed using the power spectral density (PSD) neutron noise technique known as Cohn- α , to evaluate the presence and characteristics of time correlation in the signal. The results indicate discernible non-trivial stochastic behavior in the simulated flux signals, suggesting that 'neutron noise' signatures can indeed emerge in such multiplying media. These findings indicate the potential applicability of established fission-based neutron noise methods to fusion blanket diagnostics. While the present work remains a proof of concept, it provides the first step toward developing neutron noise-based tools for monitoring, characterization, and safety analysis of future fusion reactor blanket systems.

Keywords: Power Spectral Density, Neutron Noise, Tokamak Reactor

1. INTRODUCTION

Magnetic confinement fusion has long been pursued as a clean and fuel-abundant energy source, with recent advances in devices such as ITER and DEMO bringing this goal closer to realization [1, 2]. In a Tokamak reactor, the breeding blanket plays a critical role in both tritium self-sufficiency and neutron energy conversion. Monitoring the neutron behavior within this region is important for ensuring efficient tritium breeding, thermal performance, and radiation safety. Plasma diagnostics in fusion systems are highly developed, yet diagnostics for the neutron field in the blanket region are based off established techniques, relying on activation foils, thermocouples, and global neutron yield measurements [3, 4].

In contrast, fission zero power research reactors, neutron noise analysis has been extensively employed for core diagnostics and monitoring [5, 6], integral kinetic parameter determination and non-invasive monitoring [7, 8, 9]. By studying the statistical fluctuations of the neutron flux in time or frequency domains, these methods—such as the Cohn- α or power spectral density (PSD) [10] approach, enable the identification of delayed neutron parameters, feedback mechanisms, and localized perturbations. Their strength lies in being non-invasive and sensitive to subtle changes in neutron kinetics and system reactivity.

Despite their success in fission systems, neutron noise techniques have not been systematically explored in fusion reactor environments, particularly in the breeding blankets of Tokamak devices. The neutron population in such blankets differs from that in fission cores: the energy spectrum is broader, the flux is

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highly anisotropic, and materials such as beryllium-lithium or lead-lithium introduce secondary neutron sources via (n,2n) and (n,t) reactions [11], but with lower multiplicity than fission. These multiplication effects may induce correlated temporal behavior in the neutron flux, suggesting the potential for measurable stochastic signatures [12], but this possibility has remained largely unexamined in fusion system and fusion-fission hybrid systems [13].

This work presents a preliminary computational study to assess the feasibility of applying neutron noise analysis to a multiplying fusion blanket environment. Using the Monte Carlo particle transport code OpenMC [14], a simplified Tokamak breeding blanket model containing beryllium as a neutron multiplier was simulated. A virtual ^3He detector was positioned outside the blanket to record time-dependent neutron flux signals.

The recorded data were analyzed using the Cohn- α (power spectral density) method to identify potential time correlations arising from neutron multiplication effects. The results reveal discernible stochastic behavior in the simulated signals, demonstrating that neutron noise signatures can emerge even in fusion-relevant multiplying media. This approach has the potential to support the experimental determination of kinetic information in multiplying breeding blankets, providing input for reactor design and non-invasive reactor diagnostics.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the theoretical background relevant to this study. Section 3 introduces the power spectral density (PSD) method, describes the OpenMC neutron transport code employed, and outlines the geometry of the simulated Tokamak breeding blanket model. Section 4 presents and interprets the simulation results. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the key findings of this investigation and highlights possible directions for future research.

2. THEORY OF NEUTRON NOISE

This section introduces the point kinetics equations and the idea of neutron noise induced by (n,2n) branching reactions in breeding multiplying blankets.

2.1. Point kinetics equation (PKE)

In fission reactor physics, the time evolution of the neutron density, $n(t)$, can often be approximated by the PKE, shown in Equation 1. This formulation introduces the reactivity ρ , the effective delayed neutron fraction β_{eff} , the prompt neutron generation time Λ as so-called kinetic parameters of a system driven by an external source S [15]:

$$\frac{dn(t)}{dt} = \frac{\rho - \beta_{\text{eff}}}{\Lambda} n(t) + \sum_i \lambda_i C_i + S, \quad (1)$$

where λ_i and C_i represent the decay constant and precursor concentration of the i -th delayed neutron group, respectively.

The reactivity ρ is defined in terms of the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} as follows:

$$\rho = \frac{k_{\text{eff}} - 1}{k_{\text{eff}}}, \quad k_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\bar{\nu} \Phi \Sigma_f}{\Phi \Sigma_a + \text{Leakage}}, \quad (2)$$

where:

- $\bar{\nu}$ is the average number of neutrons emitted per fission,
- Σ_f is the macroscopic fission cross section,
- Σ_a is the macroscopic absorption cross section,
- *Leakage* represents neutron losses due to escape from the system.

In the case of a fusion breeding blanket composed of beryllium and lithium, the induced neutron multiplication mechanism differs from that of a fission system. Here, the induced neutron production arises primarily from $(n, 2n)$ reactions in beryllium and tritium breeding reactions in lithium, with no contribution from delayed neutrons.

2.2. Neutron Branching

In both fission and $(n, 2n)$ reactions, neutron production is inherently stochastic, giving rise to what is known as the neutron branching process. Each neutron interaction can lead to the emission of a number of secondary neutrons, whose subsequent histories depend on the outcome of previous events. As discussed by Williams [12], this branching behavior introduces temporal correlations in the neutron population, since the occurrence of a neutron at time t is statistically related to earlier interactions in the system.

These correlations produce fluctuations in the neutron density that deviate from a purely Poisson process [16]. In other words, the variance in the neutron count exceeds that expected from independent events, leading to what is commonly referred to as neutron noise. Such noise carries physical information about the underlying multiplication mechanisms and kinetics of the medium. By analyzing these stochastic fluctuations, it becomes possible to extract integral kinetic parameters—such as the prompt neutron lifetime, reactivity, or multiplication factor—without perturbing the system. This principle forms the theoretical foundation of neutron noise analysis in fission multiplying systems, and we hypothesize that it applies to fusion as well.

In fission reactors, the directly measurable integral kinetic parameter is the prompt neutron decay constant [9], α , defined as:

$$\alpha = \frac{\rho - \beta_{\text{eff}}}{\Lambda}, \quad \frac{dn(t)}{dt} = \alpha n(t) + \sum_i \lambda_i C_i + S, \quad (3)$$

where α characterizes the average frequency at which the prompt neutron fission chain decays in a self-sustained reaction. In other words, α represents the prompt decay rate.

By analogy, an equivalent parameter should exist for the multiplying medium in a fusion breeding blanket. Unlike the fission case, no delayed neutron terms are present, and the neutron multiplication arises purely from $(n, 2n)$. We hypothesize that these time correlations could be experimentally observed through neutron noise analysis, as commonly done in fission systems [7]. Such an approach would provide a non-invasive means of characterizing the neutron multiplication dynamics within fusion blanket materials.

3. METHODS

In this section, we introduce the Power Spectral Density (PSD) method, the OpenMC code, and the model used in this work.

3.1. Cohn- α Method

The Cohn- α method [10] uses the Power Spectral Density (PSD) to perform frequency-domain analysis of time-dependent neutron detector signals. It provides a means of identifying time correlations associated with neutron population fluctuations, particularly those arising from branching processes, thereby allowing the estimation of kinetic parameters such as the prompt decay constant α .

The PSD of a stationary signal $x(t)$ can be estimated from the squared magnitude of its Fourier transform, also known as the periodogram. The analytical expression can be written as:

$$G_{xx}(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i\omega t} p(t) dt = C \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2}, \quad (4)$$

where $G_{xx}(\omega)$ is the power spectral density, ω is the angular frequency, and α represents the prompt decay constant. The term $p(t)$ denotes the autocorrelation function of the neutron signal. As shown in the equation, the resulting PSD exhibits a Lorentzian profile with a cutoff frequency proportional to α as shown in Equation 3.1.

$$\alpha = 2\pi \cdot f_c \quad (5)$$

This method can also be extended to evaluate correlations between two spatially separated detectors using the Cross Power Spectral Density (CPSD), which characterizes the frequency-dependent coherence between detector signals. However, in this work, the analysis is restricted to the single-detector PSD case.

Originally used to identify branching chains in fission systems [10], we expect this method to yield similar patterns in a breeding multiplying blanket, i.e. a Lorentzian PSD with a characteristic cutoff frequency is anticipated.

3.2. The OpenMC Code

OpenMC is an open-source, community-driven Monte Carlo particle transport code developed for simulating neutron and photon interactions [14]. It has found widespread application in nuclear engineering, fusion energy research, medical physics, and radiation shielding. Designed for high-performance computing and scalability, OpenMC is well suited for modern, large-scale simulations. Since its initial release in 2012, the code has evolved through continuous contributions from an active international user community. It features advanced geometry modeling, continuous-energy cross sections, and integration with multiphysics frameworks. In the present work, model of a Tokamak blanket reactor was developed using OpenMC.

3.3. Blanket Model

The geometry was modeled in OpenMC using its Python API based on constructive solid geometry (CSG). The configuration consists of concentric spherical regions representing a simplified section of a Tokamak breeding blanket, as illustrated in Figures 1. The inner boundary is a hollow sphere of radius 10 cm, surrounded by a beryllium–lithium (Be–Li) mixture extending to an outer radius of 25.5 cm, resulting in a blanket thickness of 15.5 cm. A cylindrical ^3He detector with a diameter of 10 cm was positioned just outside the blanket to record neutron flux time series.

This simplified configuration serves as a proof-of-concept model to assess the feasibility of applying neutron noise analysis techniques to fusion blanket environments, rather than to reproduce the full complexity of an operational Tokamak blanket.

Figure 1. 3D representation of the geometry used in the simulation. The beryllium-lithium blanket, in orange, was sectioned to reveal the hollow interior. At the center of the hollow sphere, a source S of 14.1 MeV isotropic neutrons was placed. The red cylindrical element represents the ${}^3\text{He}$ detector used in this study.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two simulation cases were performed using the OpenMC model described in Section 3.3. In both cases, a fixed isotropic neutron source S emitting 14.1 MeV neutrons was simulated over a time interval of 0 to 1 s to establish the reference source condition.

In the first case, individual $(n, 2n)$ events occurring within the blanket were tracked using the `collision_track` feature in OpenMC [17, 18, 19], in order to capture the intrinsic time correlations arising from neutron multiplication without the background fluctuations associated with the fixed source. In the second case, the `collision_track` option was restricted to interactions occurring within the ${}^3\text{He}$ detector, focusing on solely absorption events by the ${}^3\text{He}$ nuclide.

For both cases, the resulting time series were reconstructed from the recorded collision data, and the Power Spectral Density (PSD) analysis described in Section 3.1 was applied to investigate the stochastic characteristics of the neutron flux fluctuations. The PSD results for the first and second cases are shown in Figures 2 and 3, respectively.

As shown in Figure 2, the PSD corresponding to the $(n, 2n)$ interactions exhibits a clear correlation structure, with a well-defined Lorentzian shape with a cutoff frequency f_c . This behavior is expected, as the signal originates directly from neutron branching processes without interference from background noise. In contrast, the PSD obtained from the ${}^3\text{He}$ detector (Figure 3) appears noisier due to the inclusion of absorption events and statistical fluctuations due to less tracked data, which reflects the detection efficiency. Nevertheless, the fitted curve still captures a cutoff frequency f_c value consistent with that obtained from the pure $(n, 2n)$ case.

The fitted parameters extracted from the PSD analysis for both cases are summarized in Table I.

It is worth noting that, for the Lorentzian fitting, a constant term close to zero was added to stabilize the fit by accounting for background white noise, mainly originating from the isotropic 14.1 MeV source. The curves were normalized using this same constant.

To verify the causal link between the branching process and the signal correlation, $(n, 2n)$ reactions were

Figure 2. PSD of the time series collected from $(n, 2n)$ interactions in the blanket.

Figure 3. PSD of the time series collected from absorption events in the ^3He detector.

Table I. Summary of results obtained from fitting the PSD analysis.

Case	$f_c \pm \sigma_{f_c}$ (Hz)	Relative Error (%)
Tracking $(n, 2n)$ interactions	$(6.543 \pm 0.016) \times 10^7$	–
Tracking absorption in ^3He	$(7.1 \pm 0.3) \times 10^7$	8.5

manually suppressed for a separate test. Figure 4 shows that the removal of $(n, 2n)$ reactions eliminates the correlated component of the spectrum. This confirms that the correlations are an emergent property of the branching $(n, 2n)$ chains within the blanket, and not just a property of the transport itself.

Figure 4. PSD of time series collected from absorption events in the ^3He detector. The blue line represents the standard simulation, while the orange line corresponds to the case with $(n, 2n)$ reactions omitted.

We next investigated different blanket configurations. Several simulations were performed by tracking the $(n, 2n)$ reaction to maximize the visibility of the time correlation, as shown in Figure 5.

These preliminary results show distinct cutoff frequencies for different blanket compositions; for Be_{12}Ti and BeO , the cutoff frequencies are the same. Moreover, variations in the Lorentzian amplitude are

Figure 5. PSD of the time series collected from $(n, 2n)$ interactions in the blanket for different materials.

also observed. This is promising, as it suggests that additional information may be encoded in both the amplitude and the cutoff frequency of the PSD. Developing appropriate theoretical models will be important for interpreting these results quantitatively.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates that time correlations appear in the breeding multiplying blanket of a Tokamak, analogous to those found in conventional fission reactors. These correlations imply a potential of application of neutron noise methods to fusion systems for monitoring, design, and possibly safety diagnostics in future fusion reactors.

Future work includes establishing a theoretical framework to explain the observed behavior and on validating these results using a more realistic Tokamak blanket geometry and improved source modeling in Monte Carlo simulations.

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